

TEACHING THROUGH FLIPPING CLASSROOMS USING “UNICRAFT” PLATFORM

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ABSTRACT

Teaching in the modern world is at its peak and old teaching methods are beginning to lose their significance; instead, various methods emerged that are far superior to the traditional method. Due to the fact that many new different methods have appeared, the shortcomings of the traditional one has become noticeable, and this method has become ineffective. In today's world, it's nearly hard to picture studying without the use of cutting-edge technology. Today's training must fulfill the expectations of society, youth, and employers, which will be accomplished via the use of modern technology and current teaching techniques. As a result of these demands teachers frequently face difficulties in choosing the best method of teaching. In arrange to progress the quality of learning, the author of this article presents the concept of the Flipped Classroom method.

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, there have been quite a lot of adjustments in the sphere of education. Digital learning is regularly being improved, where the student is not an object of gaining knowledge but a main character in which he himself affects his development. It is no longer continually feasible to without difficulty combine old materials and methods into a new educational sphere. At the side of difficulties, potentials additionally appeared, since primary goal of current teaching system is not the amount of materials learned, but the scholar's consciousness as a separate impartial individual with creative, critical thinking and virtual competence, the person who can select individual teaching approach for

himself. All of these qualities also contribute to the formation of intelligence and flexibility to contemporary realities. On the way to form a specialist in the 21st century, the instructor should create effective technological surroundings appropriate for students, suitable for their individual progress. With this approach, it becomes necessary to search for means and ways to integrate new learning formats into the educational process within the digital educational environment. So, to improve the quality of teaching a foreign language in a technical university, a blended learning model is used [1, p.28] which allows you to introduce new technologies without abandoning traditional teaching methods. I accept as true with that mixed learning better

engages college students in mastering due to the interactivity of the educational manner. In this article, I will look up to the idea of flip classes generation, in addition to the possibility of using this technology with the usage of the academic platform "Unicraft" and conclusions concerning the effectiveness of this approach.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this article, I would like to demonstrate the possibility of making the lesson developed by me via the use of the innovative method "flipped classroom" based at the platform "Unicraft". The above data provides a thorough picture of the concept's content. Flip class and the advantages of utilizing it, so what follows is about the potential outcomes of making classes for specialized courses utilizing the internet based "Unicraft" platform. I used the technique Flipped Class with the "Unicraft" platform in foreign language courses. designed to teach a specific language within "Integration of language skills" (listening, speaking, writing and reading). The factors that make this platform unique are its features such as:

- including a built-in course editor, by which the trainers can create theoretical and practical lessons.
- the ability to construct classes using video, audio, and text;
- assistance with course formats: SCORM 1.2, SCORM 2004, AICC and Tin Can;
- the ability to create individual training programs for each user
- the capacity to administer user groups on an individual basis;
- import of materials from YouTube, Vimeo and Google Docs, support for dialogue simulators;
- gamification;

- the ability to monitor the progress of students;
- user import and integration with 1C, Bitrix-24, SAP, Active Directory, AmoCRM.

Theoretical lessons are divided into **video, audio** and **text with pictures**. Text illustrations can be either made on the platform in the inherent proofreader, or downloaded as an instant record or a connection to Google Docs. Audio and video instructional exercises can either be transferred to the platform, or you can give a connection to YouTube or Vimeo.

Practical lessons are created in the built-in editor. This lesson is better using in checking the knowledge of students, as a concluding part of a course. It can be: multiple-choice questions or tasks with a detailed answer, which are checked manually by the trainer;

The exam is the final task, where the students must give a more comprehensive answer. The exam verifies the final knowledge of the course, and when added, it is automatically placed at the end of the course.

How to check the student's answers. Students' answers can either be acknowledged by granting the Order of the most recognized, or leave a comment and ask for explanation, the coach doesn't have the choice to "Not accept" the response.

III. RESEARCH RESULTS

Using online platform "Unicraft" with a modern flipped class method, I made the following conclusions: this platform allows you to quickly create courses and has an intuitive interface and pleasant design. Furthermore, one of the most important aspects of this platform was the presence of a point of gamification, which made lessons interesting and effective, and made

students being more involved in the learning process. And the last but not the least point is the ability to supplement materials at any time with automatic additional training of students. As a general rule, the capacity to choose, work out explicit instructive material, and obviously exhibit it utilizing intelligent video permits you to increase the instructive interaction and carry out a customized approach to learning, just as follow the standard of nonlinearity.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As we can visually perceive from the current development of technology,

education should not stop in one place, utilizing the same methods and materials, since developing humanity needs everything innovative, including the field of inculcation, incipient methods utilizing the latest technologies, more and more efficacious, which gives a result in the form of a person who can individually achieve only with the avail of technology. And predicated on research conducted in higher edification institutions, the utilization of the "Flipped Classes" methodology with different online learning platforms is efficacious and has become an integral part of learning.

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